

Securing xApps in Open RAN: A Hierarchical Approach to Authentication and Authorisation

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Abstract—The Open Radio Access Network (RAN) represents a significant advancement in the ongoing evolution of mobile networks, transitioning from proprietary physical hardware to virtualised network functions. Open RAN advocates for a disaggregated RAN utilising commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) hardware. The O-RAN Alliance is the preeminent organisation in the Open RAN initiative, guiding the industry towards a vendor-neutral radio access network characterised by open interfaces and protocols. The introduction of RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs) and the ability to deploy third-party services on these RICs expedite the innovation within the RAN. The two RICs, non-real-time RIC and near-real-time RIC, enhance the operation of RAN by facilitating the deployment of third-party services, either as an rApp for non-real-time RIC or as an xApp for near-real-time RIC. However, this new disaggregated and open RAN expands the threat surface and introduces novel security and privacy challenges that were previously absent, and these issues remain unaddressed. The introduction of new stakeholders, such as third-party application providers and cloud service providers, into the RAN ecosystem presents potential vulnerabilities. This paper proposes a hierarchical management strategy to tackle security challenges in Open RAN, enabling authorisation, authentication, and monitoring for third-party applications. Experimental evaluations across multiple configurations demonstrate that the proposed framework is scalable and imposes minimal overhead, making it a practical solution for securing next-generation RAN deployments.

Index Terms—5G, Open RAN, Security, xApp

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern cellular networks are founded on a well-established centralised design, often comprising Radio Access Networks (RAN) and Core Networks (CN). The increasing demand for distributed applications across multiple sectors [1], such as Industry 4.0, autonomous driving, and Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), renders this design increasingly inadequate. Centralised designs suffer from significant communication delays and severe data privacy concerns, as critical information must traverse centralised core networks that are often distant from the end user. Consequently, attention has moved to private/local 5G networks that use edge computing and alter network topology [2]. This transition enhances latency, privacy, and security by enabling essential activities such as identity management and authentication to take place nearer

to the data source [2], [3].

The deployment of next-generation mobile networks is well underway. Functions previously implemented as Physical Network Functions (PNFs) on proprietary hardware have transitioned to Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) running on commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) servers [4]. This shift enables scalable and flexible deployment of 5G RANs and 5G CNs in virtualised environments on the cloud. Today, 5G is no longer a concept but a reality, with numerous operators worldwide rolling out deployments. Notably, around 70% of network management costs in 5G are concentrated in the RAN, driven by novel requirements such as utilising more spectrum, upgrading equipment, and the deployment of extensive small-cell networks [5].

From the 5G RAN perspective, a significant architectural evolution is underway, transitioning from LTE to next-generation RAN (NG-RAN) and Open RAN (O-RAN) [3], [6]–[9]. This involves a shift from physically distributed base stations to centrally managed stations with loosely coupled control functions. The NG-RAN consists of base stations referred to as next-generation NodeB (gNB). The NG-RAN introduces a segmentation to the gNB, assigning higher protocol layers to the centralised unit (CU) and entrusting the lower protocol stacks to the Distributed Unit (DU) [10]. This functional restructuring of RAN at lower layers presents numerous opportunities for innovation, including enhanced privacy through features supporting a decoupled RAN architecture [3]. Following the disaggregation and softwarisation of the RAN proposed by the 3GPP TR 38.801 specification [11], a functional split allows virtualised logical entities to host different layers of the radio stack. The Open RAN initiative, spearheaded by the O-RAN Alliance, is advancing this disaggregated network architecture towards vendor-neutral deployments by advocating open and standardised interfaces and protocols. These efforts are reshaping the industry, fostering interoperability, flexibility, and a competitive ecosystem.

The Open RAN architecture established by the O-RAN Alliance comprises two RAN Intelligent Controllers (RICs) functioning in a hierarchical structure. These offer programmability, automation, and intelligence to the RAN. The near-real-

time (near-RT) RIC is implemented at the network’s edge and executes control loops with a duration ranging from 10 ms to 1 s [7], [12]. The primary function of the near-RT RIC is to manage and enhance the RAN through its engagement with DUs and CUs, in addition to interfacing with legacy O-RAN-compliant LTE evolved NodeB (eNB) systems [7]. These nodes are referred to as E2 nodes, as the near-RT RIC communicates with and controls these entities through the functionalities provided by the E2 interface. The near-RT RIC is readily programmable, enabling the deployment of third-party services or utility VNFs as xApps within it [4]. This grants Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) significant autonomy in accessing and managing information within the RAN using a software-defined approach. Due to the decentralised and modular characteristics of the Open RAN network, xApps are created as microservices instead of being integrated as a monolithic function within a single VNF [4]. This raises a need for inter-xApp communication. The near-RT RIC possesses characteristics including conflict prevention, a subscription manager, and a shared data layer (SDL) to support this. Nonetheless, additional enhancements in service discovery, authorisation, and authentication are required to enable secure and efficient inter-xApp communication on a large scale. The non-real-time (non-RT) RIC, similarly, facilitates closed-loop control of the RAN with timescales exceeding 1 s [7]. Non-RT RIC resides within the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework, which is tasked with orchestrating, managing, and automating functions to monitor and control all RAN elements. Non-RT RIC also facilitates the implementation of third-party apps known as rApps, which assist with RAN control and optimisation, encompassing policy guidance, information enrichment, configuration management, and data analytics. rApps can offer comparable control functions to xApps over extended timescales. They concentrate on formulating control policies that function at a higher level and influence a larger number of users and network nodes. The A1 interface links the two RICs, enabling the non-RT RIC to offer policy-driven direction to the near-RT RIC [7].

Fig. 1 illustrates the high-level integration of O-RAN into the 5G architecture. The near-RT RIC can be implemented alongside various logical entities inside the O-RAN architecture based on deployment specifications. The deployment of xApps may influence the latency of services utilising xApps due to the near-RT RIC’s position. Consequently, the strategic positioning of the near-RT RIC is a design factor. In the illustration, the near-RT RIC is co-located with the CU, which is divided into the control plane (O-CU-CP) and user plane (O-CU-UP). The O-RAN components, including DU, CU, near-RT RIC, non-RT RIC, and SMO, can be implemented in the cloud or proximate to the sites on physical COTS hardware using virtualisation. In Fig. 1, the SMO and non-RT RIC are implemented in a central cloud infrastructure together with the 5G CN.

This paper aims to design a comprehensive framework for the authorisation, authentication, and monitoring of third-party

applications (i.e., xApps and rApps). To achieve this, we propose a hierarchical security model that aligns with the hierarchical structure of the RICs in the O-RAN architecture, which are organised based on timescales. This alignment ensures a clear separation of concerns, allowing security-related decisions to be made at appropriate levels depending on the timescale. As part of this model, we utilise JSON Web Tokens (JWTs) for access control. Specifically, we improve the token granting mechanism of the existing XRF framework [4], providing additional security features aligned with modern authorisation practices. While this paper presents the overall architecture, the scope of this work focuses on evaluating the access control component, particularly the improved token issuance mechanism. The performance of the proposed system was tested compared to a baseline XRF framework.

The subsequent sections of the paper are structured as follows: Section II examines current initiatives to secure xApps. Section III describes the threat model. Section IV explains the framework design and the proposed integration of O-RAN. Section V delineates the experiment designed to assess the proposed system. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORKS

This section summarises prior research on securing third-party applications (e.g., xApps or rApps) and their running environments (i.e., RICs). The O-RAN Alliance has delineated a set of specifications [13]–[20] through the O-RAN Alliance Security Work Group (WG11) that enables mobile network operators to implement an open RAN that complies with industry standards for an open, interoperable, and secure system. The O-RAN Alliance Security Focus Group (SFG) was transformed into a comprehensive technical working group (WG11) in 2022, with an increased focus on security. The authors of [7] have presented an overview of O-RAN architecture, interfaces, research problems, and security, summarising the efforts of O-RAN WG 11. The O-RAN Alliance Technical Report (TR) on security for near real-time RIC and xApps [13] has identified several critical issues, such as malicious and compromised xApps, API vulnerabilities, conflicting xApps, and the protection of sensitive UE and RAN data. The TR emphasised the need for robust authentication and authorisation frameworks, such as JWTs and Mutual Transport Layer Security (mTLS), to ensure secure xApp onboarding and API-level authentication and access control. Additionally, it underscored the importance of adopting Zero Trust Architecture and safeguarding Machine Learning (ML) models deployed as xApps.

T. O. Atalay et al. in [4] introduced the xApp Repository Function (XRF) framework and how it can help secure xApp deployment and communication using access tokens. XRF is a microservice-based extension to the near-RT RIC that provides authentication, authorisation, and a service discovery mechanism for xApps. XRF serves as a local metadata database and an OAuth 2.0 [21] server for the xApps, issuing JWTs as access tokens. The authors have highlighted that JWTs are more beneficial for the proposed framework’s scalability as

Fig. 1: High-level Overview of the O-RAN 5G Ecosystem

the tokens are self-contained and do not require server-side storage. The authors tested the system in a containerised environment and claim that the proposed framework scales well in a multithreaded microservice model environment. O-RAN Alliance TR on OAuth 2.0 Security [19] also emphasises the importance of JWTs for the authorisation of RAN elements. However, JWTs have some inherent limitations. By default, JWTs are not encrypted, leaving them vulnerable to exposure if transmitted without adequate security measures. Furthermore, due to the stateless nature of JWTs, the revocation of access tokens poses significant challenges, and the TR [19] has emphasised the necessity of establishing procedures for token revocation. Moreover, the risks of token hijacking or leakage are present as critical vulnerabilities.

A. S. Abdalla et al. in [22] discuss how to leverage zero trust principles for deploying xApps in O-RAN. The authors present Zero Trust RAN (ZTRAN), which incorporates service authentication, intrusion detection, and a slicing mechanism executed as xApps. The authors examine a scenario with mission-critical users requiring safe and robust communication. The authors contend that using the zero trust paradigm can safeguard RAN through robust authentication techniques, the application of network segmentation, and the streamlining of access policies. The authors employed two logical components, the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) and the Policy Decision Point (PDP), to facilitate zero-trust features in the implementations. These two entities issue and verify authentication tokens or credentials to ensure secure access for authenticated users. In accordance with the least privilege zero trust principles, the UEs and RAN nodes are allocated only the essential resources required for authentication throughout the verification phase. Upon verification, a UE will be allocated to a network slice that satisfies the resource requirements specified by the service type. The slicing xApp, in conjunction with the intrusion detection xApp, reallocates UEs showing anomalous behaviour to restricted and isolated slices. The authors implemented and evaluated their proposed solution using the Open Artificial Intelligence Cellular (OAIC) research platform, which utilises the near-RT RIC interfaces and processes provided by the O-RAN Software Community (OSC). The authors state that the experimental findings demonstrate enhanced throughput and latency performance for legitimate users through the prompt identification of intruders with the proposed system.

Several studies [3], [5], [23] in the literature examine the use of decentralized approaches, such as Distributed Ledger

Technologies (DLTs), particularly blockchain, in Open RAN. Currently, there exists a paucity of research articles addressing the security of xApps through the utilisation of DLTs. Z. A. El Houda et al. in [23] introduced the TrustORAN framework. This is a blockchain-based zero-trust framework designed to enhance the security of O-RAN. The authors suggest a two-stage authentication and authorisation approach employing smart contracts operating on the blockchain to oversee the authentication and authorisation of xApps. In the proposed system, a vendor utilises an Access Control Contract (ACC) to regulate access to specified xApps. Each ACC includes a mapping for access control pertaining to a subject (i.e., xApps or near-RT RIC) and the resources of an object (i.e., xApps). ACC comprises numerous tuples that signify specific parameters, such as access tokens to indicate subject-object pairs. Access tokens are generated by a specific xApp called the Control xApp (CxApp). The CxApp also performs mutual authentication with the access-requesting xApp to ensure secure interactions. To access a resource, the subject presents its token along with the request to the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP), which verifies the token's validity and enforces the defined policies. The authors have assessed the proposed system on both private and public Ethereum blockchains, asserting that the results demonstrate the system's scalability, lightweight nature, and cost-effectiveness. L. Giupponi and F. Wilhelmi in [5] and H. Xu et al. in [3] examine the potential of blockchain for enhancing the security of the O-RAN ecosystem through different modifications to the fundamental architecture. This, however, does not directly address the effects on xApps or rApps, nor does it provide details regarding the access control or authorisation processes.

III. THREAT MODEL

The O-RAN architecture is founded on the principles and specifications set forth by 3GPP for the 5G and beyond RAN. The additional entities, interfaces, and functions added by O-RAN considerably extend the attack surface of the base 5G RAN architecture. The near-RT RIC introduces third-party xApps that can control RAN operations. This introduces novel risks such as malware xApps or xApps with excessive privileges [16]. Moreover, open-source code could utilise modules with known vulnerabilities and untrusted libraries that might be exploited by an attacker via a backdoor attack [4], [16]. This section defines our adversarial model, specifying the assumptions, attack vectors, and security considerations. Our threat

model closely resembles that of the XRF framework [4], since we adopted the XRF framework with several modifications to the token granting process.

We assume the presence of both passive and active adversaries capable of intercepting communications between xApps and between xApps and the authentication server. In addition, an inherent lack of trust is presumed between third-party app vendors and MNOs. The deployment environment is assumed to be secure against virtualisation-based attacks that target sandbox environments (e.g., containers, virtual machines) by leveraging advanced techniques such as remote attestation. The trusted entities are presumed to be free from the adversary’s control and/or located in a secure environment. The adversary may exert some control over the untrusted entities.

Trusted entities

- O-RAN E2, nodes including RU, DU, and CU
- O-RAN central deployment, including SMO, non-RT RIC and interfaces to the near-RT RIC
- Management and Orchestration (MANO) entity that manages the virtualised infrastructure, resource allocation, and network function lifecycle management.

Untrusted entities

- Third-party app (xApp/rApp) vendors
- RICs (near-RT and non-RT) (assumed to be vulnerable to malicious eavesdroppers)

A. Attacker Model

Actor: Malicious third-party xApps, set up via the SMO into the near-RT RIC, aim to subscribe to RAN nodes for the sake of eavesdropping or interrupting RAN operations.

Objectives: Malicious xApps exploit weaknesses in authentication and authorisation mechanisms to get unauthorised access to other deployed xApps and the internal communications of the near-RT RIC. This may impair the service to genuine xApps and influence a RAN node’s performance or QoS goals. A malicious xApp with passive behaviour can use RAN nodes to eavesdrop on sensitive information, such as tracking user whereabouts or inferring user identities [4]. An active attacker may escalate their actions by modifying or injecting messages, compromising the integrity of data handled by RAN nodes or other legitimate xApps [16].

Capabilities: The malicious xApp can access information within the near-RT RIC internal messaging infrastructure prior to subscribing to other endpoints.

B. Attack Vector

Fig. 2 depicts the attack vector employed to accomplish the objectives. The green lines denote the trustworthy entities, whereas the red lines signify the untrusted entities. In step 1, an xApp vendor initiates the deployment of the xApp using the SMO. The SMO, as indicated in step 2, thereafter instructs the near-RT RIC to deploy the xApp. Step 3 illustrates the deployment of the malicious xApp, whereas step 4 demonstrates the xApp’s access to the message infrastructure and the E2 termination (e.g., RAN stack). A passive malicious

xApp can access APIs and sensitive information, whereas an active malicious xApp can compromise the system by changing data and impersonating legitimate xApps, resulting in adverse consequences.

Fig. 2: Attack Vector Propagation

IV. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

This section explains the design of a hierarchical security framework to enhance the security of third-party applications within the RAN.

A. A Hierarchical Model

The framework is structured to match the varying operational timescales of these applications. At the highest tier, there are rApps, which operate inside the non-RT RIC. These apps typically make decisions that affect numerous users or network components. Examples include frequency management, RAN sharing, performance diagnostics, end-to-end Service Level Agreement (SLA) assurance, and network slicing [7]. Following that, xApps that operate in the near-RT, often executing control loops with a period of 10 ms to 1 s. Examples encompass load balancing and mobility management. Finally, there is a growing category of apps known in the literature as distributed applications (dApps) [24], [25], which operate directly on RAN components such as the CU and DU. The objective of dApps is to regulate real-time control loops with durations under 10 ms, catering to more stringent timelines than those of the RICs. Examples include resource allocation, beamforming, and modulation [25]. The idea of dApps (control loops under 10 ms) is not yet defined in the O-RAN Alliance specifications as of this writing. We propose including dApps into this framework, as they correspond perfectly with the hierarchical model we advocate. This hierarchical security structure is inspired by the tiered approach of the RICs, which differentiate operations according to timescales. We suggest using a hierarchical structure to oversee the security of the RAN, emphasising authentication, authorisation, and monitoring for third-party services, including rApps, xApps, and dApps. Fig. 3 presents an overview of the control flow in the proposed security model.

The proposed model advocates for the implementation of a dedicated security app at every level of the architecture. This comprises a dedicated dApp, xApp, and rApp for security at their respective levels. These dedicated security applications perform horizontal monitoring and report security-related data to the subsequent higher tier. The objective is to avoid unnecessary expenditure of time and resources on computationally intensive tasks, such as extensive data analysis, at lower tiers. Security-related data collected at lower tiers is forwarded to the rApp in the non-RT RIC, where it could be analysed. Additionally, this approach enables innovative solutions for AI/ML-powered security assessments. According to O-RAN specifications, the SMO and non-RT RIC are designed to collect data via the O1 interface, develop, train, and test ML models, and deploy them as xApps through the A1 interface to deliver new services. A similar approach can be adopted for managing security-related data. The rApps in the non-RT RIC have the necessary resources to perform preprocessing, filtering, and feature extraction from the raw data collected at each tier. Moreover, the security rApp can evaluate ML models planned for deployment as xApps for potential security vulnerabilities. Mitigating vulnerabilities in ML models is a key concern highlighted in the O-RAN specifications [13]. At the non-RT RIC level, the system has adequate resources to perform advanced model evaluation techniques and simulate attacks to assess the robustness and security of ML models. This dedicated security app at each tier is perceived as a singular entity by external systems. However, they can leverage multiple instances of the same app for load balancing, supported by proxies, to handle excessive data flow efficiently.

Fig. 3: Hierarchical Architecture

B. Modified XRF Framework

We utilise XRF [4] as an OAuth 2.0 server [21] to issue JWT-based access tokens. However, existing work on JWT-based authentication possesses certain drawbacks, including token hijacking and revocation challenges, as outlined in Section II. To mitigate the risk of malicious actors exploiting compromised tokens, short-lived access tokens can be employed. However, this approach introduces superfluous overhead, as legitimate applications are required to frequently request new tokens upon expiration, potentially increasing system load. To address these challenges, we propose several modifications. The primary modification involves utilising *refresh tokens* with

a shortened expiration time, providing a more secure and efficient token management mechanism. The authorisation server must preserve the association between a refresh token and the client (i.e., xApp) to which it was granted. Refresh tokens must exclusively be transmitted via TLS, as specified in the standard [21]. Fig. 4 illustrates the working mechanism of refresh tokens with several steps. In step 1, the xApp (the client) requests an access token from the OAuth 2.0 authorisation server, which is integrated within the XRF server. In step 2, the server provides an access token and a refresh token. Both tokens are issued with expiration times; typically, the access token holds a brief lifespan, but the refresh token remains active for a longer time. In step 3.a, the client utilises a valid access token to request access to a protected resource (e.g., another xApp). As demonstrated in step 4.a, the request is successful, and the resource is retrieved. If the client employs an expired or invalid access token, as illustrated in step 4.b, the protected resource will return an error indicating the token's invalidity or expiration. In this situation, as demonstrated in step 5, the client can use the valid refresh token to request a new access token from the authorisation server. In step 6, the server provides a new access token and, if refresh token rotation is activated, also delivers a new refresh token while invalidating the prior one.

Fig. 4: Access with Refresh Tokens

The authorisation server could implement procedures like refresh token rotation [21] to enhance the security of the refresh tokens. In refresh token rotations, the server provides a new refresh token with each access token refresh response. The prior refresh token is rendered invalid but preserved by the authorisation server. Fig. 5 depicts the interaction the authentication server and its storage for this process.

Fig. 5: Refresh Token Rotation

Refresh token rotation should have a mechanism to address

token leakage problem. Should a refresh token be compromised and utilised by both the attacker and the authorised client, one party will present an invalidated refresh token, thereby notifying the authorisation server of the breach [21]. As the authorisation server tracks the association between the active refresh token and the previously invalidated refresh tokens, as seen in Fig. 5, it can implement suitable measures to mitigate malicious activities. Fig. 6 depicts a methodology commonly utilised in authorisation systems. Step 1 illustrates the leaking of the refresh token *RT1* from a valid xApp (i.e., client) to a malicious client. This may occur as a result of improper token storage or the use of insecure transmission methods. Step 2 outlines the process for acquiring a new access token with a valid refresh token. Step 3 shows the issuance of a new access token *AT2* and a refresh token *RT2*, with token rotation enabled. Subsequently, the server invalidates the refresh token *RT1* while maintaining the association between *RT1* and *RT2*. When the malicious user attempts to hijack the *RT1*, as illustrated in step 4, to obtain a new access token, the server identifies the reutilisation of an invalidated refresh token. Given that the server recognises the relation between *RT1* and *RT2*, it will also invalidate *RT2*. In step 5, the server responds to the malicious client with an access denied notification. As seen in step 6, when the legitimate client attempts to obtain a new access token using *RT2*, it receives an access denied notification, as illustrated in step 7, due to the invalidity of *RT2*. Subsequently, the authorised client must re-login using valid credentials.

Fig. 6: Protection Against Token Leakage

In the proposed framework, establishing a connection between the security-xApp and the security-rApp is needed. Within the O-RAN architecture, the A1 interface enables communication between the non-RT RIC and the near-RT RIC. However, the O-RAN specifications do not explicitly define the mechanisms for P2P communication between xApps and rApps. Horizontal communication among xApps/rApps is facilitated by the internal messaging infrastructure. Additionally, the security-xApp can leverage this infrastructure to monitor internal messaging for potential anomalies.

Table I outlines the innovative aspects of the suggested security framework and its contributions to the advancement

of state-of-the-art.

V. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

This section discusses and presents the findings from the experiments conducted to evaluate the proposed system.

To evaluate the proposed security framework's effectiveness, we used two simple xApps, one as the client (xApp1) and the other as the resource (xApp2). An application for granting access tokens was developed, adhering to the OAuth 2.0 authorisation framework specifications [21] and building on previous XRF work [4].

Fig. 7 illustrates the experimental setup, with two configurations based on the placement of the XRF server. In Setup 1, both the XRF server and the xApps are located within the near-RT RIC. In Setup 2, the XRF server resides in the non-RT RIC, whereas the xApps remain in the near-RT RIC. To simulate the different RICs, we deployed each component on separate Virtual Machines (VMs). To evaluate the proposed framework under different conditions, we defined three authentication scenarios. Each scenario was tested under both Setup 1 and Setup 2.

- Case 1: Use of access tokens only.
- Case 2: Use of both access and refresh tokens.
- Case 3: Use of access and refresh tokens with token rotation.

In Case 1, the authentication server grants access tokens to an authenticated client (e.g., xApp1). A client may utilise this token to access a resource (e.g., xApp2) until its expiration. Upon expiration, the client must re-authenticate using the credentials. This is the token mechanism used in the reference XRF framework [4]. In Case 2, after successful authentication, the server provides the client with an access token and a refresh token. Generally, access tokens have a shorter lifespan, while refresh tokens are long-lived. Upon the expiration of the access token, the client may request a new access token with a valid refresh token without needing to re-authenticate, thus reducing latency. In Case 3, the same process as in Case 2 is employed, but with token rotation enabled. This means a new refresh token is issued with every access token renewal. The underlying mechanism is explained in Section IV-B and illustrated in Fig. 5. We have conducted multiple measurements, including authentication delay, refresh delay, request delay, and network bandwidth, for all potential scenarios under setup 1 and setup 2. The experiments were conducted on a personal computer with the following specifications: Intel Core Ultra 7 165H processor (16 cores, 22 threads, up to 5 GHz), 32 GB RAM, 1 TB SSD, running Ubuntu 22.04. The experiment was designed in Python with FastAPI and JavaScript Object Signing and Encryption (JOSE) library and Redis as a database.

We first measured the authentication delay for the three cases. Authentication delay quantifies the time it takes for an xApp to authenticate with the authorisation server using its credentials. This encompasses the duration required to send a

TABLE I: Originality and Innovative Aspects

Goal	State-of-the-art	Advancement beyond State-of-the-art
Secure access control for xApps	JWT-based OAuth 2.0 access control with XRF [4]	OAuth 2.0 access control with XRF using access & refresh JWTs
Improve security with minimum modification	Introduction of XRF [4], Smart contract-based access control [23]	Improve security of XRF with token rotation
Improve scalability	Microservice architecture for xApps authentication & authorisation [4]	Microservice architecture with hierarchical separation of responsibilities
Improve utilisation	Share resources as VNFs with smart contracts [5]	Share resources as VNFs using JWTs

Fig. 7: Experimental Setup

POST request to the server’s endpoint, the time required to receive and process the response, and the time needed to decode and validate the JWT token. In all three instances, the authentication procedure is analogous, as seen by the findings depicted in Fig. 8. Measurements were taken for up to 400 concurrent users attempting to authenticate simultaneously. Under Setup 1, the average authentication delays for Cases 1, 2, and 3 were 4195 ms, 4715 ms, and 4454 ms, respectively. These values fall within a similar range, indicating consistent performance across the three cases. Nevertheless, in configuration 2, there is an observable increase in authentication time across all three scenarios due to the additional latency introduced by relocating the authentication server to a separate virtual machine. The authentication delay remains consistent, measuring 7774ms, 7834ms, and 8783ms for the three situations, respectively. These results suggest that the placement of the authentication server is the primary factor influencing authentication delay in this experiment. The choice of authentication method (access tokens only, with refresh tokens, or with token rotation) does not significantly affect the delay.

Subsequently, Fig. 9 illustrates the refresh delay for Cases 2 and 3. As Case 1 does not utilise refresh tokens by design, it is excluded from this experiment. Refresh delay quantifies the duration required to renew an expired access token with a refresh token. This delay encompasses network latency, server processing time, including the validation of the refresh token and the generation of new access and refresh tokens (if token rotation is enabled), as well as client-side processing, such as JSON parsing and token decoding. The refresh action is generally faster than full authentication as it does not require

Fig. 8: Authentication Delay

credential verification. The process involves the straightforward validation of the token and the issuance of a new token. The delay is less than 100 ms, as illustrated in Fig. 9. A minor, although discernible, increase in time is observed in setup 1. The likely cause of this is the execution of multiple background processes that are measuring the experiments. No architectural or design-related factor explains this minor increase. Overall, the results demonstrate that the token refresh mechanism is highly efficient, even when the authorisation server is deployed on a separate VM, as in Setup 2.

Fig. 9: Token Refresh Delay

In this experiment, the resource was a simple string returned by xApp2. Since xApp1 and xApp2 are hosted in the same environment in both setups, the request delays remained largely consistent across both setups. Figure 10 illustrates that with up to 300 concurrent users, the request time consistently remains approximately 11 seconds. At 400 concurrent users,

the request delays under Setup 1 were 16.417 s, 15.957 s, and 12.080 s for Cases 1, 2, and 3, respectively. Under Setup 2, the delays were 13.205 s, 13.181 s, and 10.244 s, respectively. This shows a variation of up to 6 seconds, which remains within an acceptable range given the load. The likely cause of this increased variability at higher concurrency is resource saturation. The resource server likely lacked sufficient processing power to efficiently handle 400 simultaneous requests.

Fig. 10: Request Delay

In the next experiment, we quantify the network traffic for the three cases to assess bandwidth utilisation. Fig. 11 presents the total traffic exchanged during authentication and token refresh operations for each case. This experiment is conducted only in setup 1, as the payload is the same for both configurations. In Case 1, which uses only access tokens, the authentication request is 72 bytes, and the response containing the access token is 165 bytes, resulting in a total of 237 bytes of network traffic per authentication. In Case 2, the authentication request remains 72 bytes, but the response includes both an access token and a refresh token, increasing its size to 328 bytes. This results in a total of 400 bytes for the authentication. For the token refresh, the request containing the refresh token is 144 bytes, and the response containing the new access token is 165 bytes, leading to a total of 309 bytes. In Case 3, the authentication traffic is identical to Case 2, totalling 400 bytes. However, during token refresh with token rotation enabled, each new access token is accompanied by a newly issued refresh token. The request remains 144 bytes, but the response increases to 328 bytes, bringing the total traffic to 472 bytes. Fig. 11 clearly illustrates that Case 3 generates the highest network traffic due to the additional security overhead introduced by token rotation. This trade-off reflects the balance between improved security and bandwidth consumption. Nonetheless, this extra bandwidth consumption can be eased by extending the access token expiration duration, thereby decreasing the frequency of token renewals. This approach decreases network traffic but compromises security, as a longer token lifespan increases the risk of vulnerability in case of token breach.

In the next experiment, we simulate a malicious client that has acquired a compromised token. This experiment is conducted under Case 3, which comprises advanced security

Fig. 11: Network Bandwidth Consumption

features such as token rotation. The simulated attack follows the process illustrated in Fig. 6. Initially, a legitimate xApp accesses the resource using a valid access token issued by the authentication server. Upon the expiration of the access token, the xApp requests a new access token using a valid refresh token. However, if a malicious client acquires a compromised token due to inadequate token storage or insecure transmission, the malicious client can access the resource until the refresh token expires, which is rather lengthy (ranging from several minutes to several days, depending on the requirements). With token rotation enabled, this threat is mitigated. Each time a new access token is issued, a new refresh token is also generated, and the old refresh token is invalidated. The server monitors utilised refresh tokens to identify potential security breaches. If the server receives an invalidated refresh token, it cancels the current active refresh token, necessitating the client to re-authenticate. Fig. 12 shows the time taken for xApp1 to refresh its access token. In cases where the server identifies a reused or leaked refresh token, the client is required to re-authenticate, resulting in a noticeable spike in refresh time. As observed in Fig. 12, during refresh attempts 3, 6, and 13, the server detected a compromised token, forcing the legitimate xApp to re-authenticate. These events are marked in red, indicating higher refresh times. In contrast, normal refresh operations (marked in blue) remain very fast and consistent. These results confirm that the implementation in Case 3 effectively detects and responds to token leakage.

Fig. 12: Token Reuse Detection

VI. CONCLUSION

Open RAN represents a significant step forward in mobile network evolution, advocating open, standardised interfaces and protocols. It promotes the softwarization of the RAN and the adoption of COTS hardware. The O-RAN Alliance, at the forefront of this initiative, has published a reference architecture and specifications to guide researchers and network operators. However, the increased openness also expands the attack surface, necessitating robust security frameworks to mitigate emerging threats. In this paper, we proposed a hierarchical management model and introduced improvements to the XRF framework for managing authorisation for xApps. We assessed the framework across two deployment setups and three token configurations, derived from the OAuth 2.0 specification, resulting in six experimental scenarios. VMs were used to simulate distinct RIC environments. We assessed several metrics, including delays and network bandwidth utilisation for different token categories. A token hijacking scenario was simulated to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed system. The results indicate that the suggested architecture operates effectively with numerous concurrent xApps. Furthermore, it is essential to emphasise that the implementation of refresh tokens and the adoption of token rotation for improved security contribute only a minimal delay to the total operation. Nonetheless, there is a modest increase in bandwidth consumption. Setting a dynamic expiration time for access tokens based on security requirements is an intriguing prospect for future research. We also aim to improve the security evaluation of the framework by incorporating metrics such as token compromise detection time, false positive rates, and attack recovery time. The findings indicate that the proposed framework exhibits effective scalability in a multi-threaded context, and in future implementations, we anticipate deploying this configuration in a more resource-rich computing environment.

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